
97. Life on other worlds?

I WILL DEVIATE from discussing Gaia directly to review the philosophical debates that have raged since antiquity on whether ‘populated’ worlds exist beyond our own. I draw largely on the extensive literature chronicled by Michael Crowe (1986). It provides an interesting historical background to the search for exoplanets, and life on other worlds, which *are* being assisted by Gaia.

THE ANCIENTS of both Greece and Rome were already deeply divided. Arguing for the ‘plurality’ of life beyond Earth was Epicurus (341–270 BCE), who wrote ‘...there are infinite worlds both like and unlike this world of ours’, adding that ‘we must believe that in all worlds there are living creatures and plants and other things we see in this world’.

Opposition to this pluralist position dates back to at least the time of Plato and Aristotle. Plato (428–348 BCE) was confident that ‘there is and ever will be one only-begotten and created heaven’.

Post-Copernicus, Galileo Galilei, René Descartes, Pierre Gassendi and Isaac Newton viewed such speculation as being at the limit of legitimate science.

BUT BETWEEN 1500–1750, plurality gained the support of many prominent figures. As summarised by Crowe: ‘Presented with exceptional appeal by Fontenelle, given legitimacy in scientific circles by Christiaan Huygens and Isaac Newton, reconciled to religion by Richard Bentley and William Derham, ... [it was] integrated into philosophical systems by George Berkeley and Gottfried Wilhelm Leibniz, and taught in textbooks by Christian Wolff’. Many leading astronomers and philosophers of the 18–19th centuries contributed to the debate.

During the second half of the 18th century, plurality was embraced by a number of influential astronomers. Crowe argues that the writings of pioneers such as Thomas Wright, Immanuel Kant, and Johann Lambert, were permeated by pluralism and the extraterrestrial life debate. Kant’s various texts suggest that the ‘starry heavens’ that so filled him with awe were ‘a densely denizened domain wherein millions of inhabited planets orbited suns clustered in endless hierarchies of systems’.

THE RESEARCH of the period’s foremost astronomer, William Herschel, was deeply influenced by ideas of extraterrestrial life. Indeed, his genius notwithstanding, Herschel considered that the Moon had ‘the great probability, not to say absolute certainty, of being inhabited’, his lunar observations evidencing ‘vegetation’, ‘turnpike roads’, and ‘circuses’.

He referred to the ‘inhabitants’ of Mars, Saturn, and Uranus, and of their satellites, and to the fact that every star ‘is probably of as much consequence to a system of planets, satellites, and comets, as our own Sun...’, while his observations of sun spots suggested that even the Sun ‘...is most probably also inhabited... by beings whose organs are adapted to the peculiar circumstances of that vast globe’ (Herschel 1795).

Many of his renowned contemporaries, including François Arago, Jérôme Lalande, and Johann Schröter, were also involved in the quest. Johann Bode advocated extraterrestrials with fervour and influence, considering that essentially every celestial body – sun, star, planet, and satellite – was populated with rational beings.

Pierre Simon Laplace’s ‘nebular hypothesis’ of 1796 explained the solar system as resulting from the rotation and contraction of a primitive solar ‘fluid’, implying that planets are an expected result of stellar evolution, and thus providing support for the pluralist contention that most stars were encircled by planets

And from the cooling times of the Earth and planets, the Comte de Buffon even tabulated, in 1775, the times at which life began and would end on each.

PHYSICOTHEOLOGIANs embraced extraterrestrials as evidence of God’s omnipotence, while the religious authorities saw plurality as the product of divine power and generosity.

Thomas Paine’s *Age of Reason* of 1793 essentially rejected Christianity because of pluralism. James Mitchell’s lecture *On the Plurality of Worlds* to the London Mathematical Society in 1813 argued for life on all planets and satellites. Thomas Dick (1837) actually estimated the population of the solar system bodies (including the rings of Saturn!), as 21 894 974 404 480.

IN HIS *Complete System of Astronomy* of 1797–1808 Samuel Vince, Plumian Professor of Astronomy at Cambridge, considered that novae were *‘the destruction of that system at the time appointed by the Deity for the probation of its inhabitants’*.

Other eminent early 19th century astronomers were pluralists and even proponents of lunar life. Historical research suggests that Carl Friedrich Gauss proposed a giant figure in Siberia to signal to the Moon or Mars, while Johann von Littrow suggesting a kerosene-lit canal in the Sahara for similar purposes.

In a letter to the astronomer and journal editor Franz Gruithuisen, Bremen astronomer Wilhelm Olbers stated that *‘I hold it to be very probable that the Moon is inhabited by living, even rational creatures, and that something not wholly dissimilar to our vegetation occurs on the Moon’*.

SUPPORT FOR extraterrestrials received a setback with a lecture by the German astronomer, physicist and mathematician Friedrich Bessel in 1834. By appealing to the sharpness with which stars are occulted by the Moon’s limb, he argued that it lacks any significant atmosphere, and that it therefore has neither air nor water.

Hegel raised philosophical objections to plurality, and in 1853 William Whewell published an essay claiming that many of the pluralist arguments were scientifically defective and religiously dangerous.

This led to renewed debate involving, among others, physicist David Brewster, Oxford Savilian professor Baden Powell, astronomers Lord Rosse and Camille Flammarion, populariser Richard Proctor, mathematician Augustus De Morgan, and biologist Charles Darwin.

THE ADVENT OF spectroscopy, pioneered by William Huggins, Anders Ångström, Henry Draper, Jules Janssen, Joseph Norman Lockyer, and Angelo Secchi, led to more quantitative stellar investigations, but also provided further substance for the pluralist debate; in fact *‘to a greater extent than has been previously noted, [they] saw themselves as involved in that debate’*.

In their first major spectroscopic study of nearly fifty stars, Huggins & Miller (1864) identified numerous spectral lines coinciding with the terrestrial elements. And they concluded that *‘There is therefore a probability that these stars are... like our Sun, surrounded by planets.’*

And they went on: *‘It is remarkable that the elements most widely diffused through the host of stars are some of those most closely connected with the constitution of the living organisms of our globe... On the whole we believe that the foregoing [observations] contribute something towards an experimental basis on which a conclusion... may rest, viz. that at least the brighter stars are, like our sun, upholding and energising centres of systems of worlds adapted to the abode of living beings’*.

SUBSEQUENT DEBATES surrounded the suggested observational evidence for life in our solar system. Amongst these were varying features in the lunar crater Linné (Schmidt 1866; as summarised by Moore 1977); as well as consequences of the lunar figure for habitability (Hansen 1856). There were various reports of Martian or Venusian ‘signals’, involving Nikola Tesla, Lord Kelvin, and Guglielmo Marconi, as well as claims of lunar vegetation by William Henry Pickering (1902).

Even a mere 80 years ago, the then Astronomer Royal Harold Spencer Jones (1940, p207) considered it *‘almost certain that there is some form of vegetation on Mars’*.

A CENTURY AGO saw the protracted debate (1877–1910), and substantial literature, on the question of canals on Mars. Schiaparelli, Lowell, and Flammarion were the main advocates, with Antoniadi, Campbell, and Maunder leading the anti-canal and anti-life arguments.

Sixty pages in Crowe (1986), detail the controversy, its now-favoured explanation in terms of the Maunder–Cerulli theory of unconscious tendencies to see discrete details integrated into lines or circles, and more recent assessment of its context and scientific consequences (Shklovskii & Sagan 1966; Sagan & Fox 1975; Wells 1979).

TODAY, the existence of (admittedly more primitive) life elsewhere in the solar system is still under serious investigation, and the debate remains unresolved.

In the search for life on the growing number of known exoplanets, an important consideration is the optimum spectral range (optical, infrared, or both), and which spectral lines offer the best prospects of indicating the presence of life. The arguments are largely founded on carbon-based life as presently known.

THE SEARCH for extra-terrestrial *intelligence*, SETI, is motivated by the belief that intelligent life is likely to emerge under conditions similar to those on Earth.

Loosely connected but not implicit in such searches are various unproven and somewhat inconsistent postulates, amongst them the ‘anthropic principle’, which suggests that no assertion can be made about the probability of intelligent life based on a sample set of one); the ‘mediocrity principle’ (which, given the existence of life on Earth, asserts that life typically exists on Earth-like planets throughout the Universe); and the ‘fine-tuning hypothesis’ (which asserts that the natural conditions for intelligent life are implausibly rare).

Attempts to quantify the probability that intelligent life exists elsewhere in the Galaxy include consideration of the ‘Drake equation’, and of the ‘Fermi paradox’, viz. *‘If other advanced civilisations exist, where are they?’*. Resolution of these questions may still lie far in the future.

This essay is based on my text in The Exoplanet Handbook, Cambridge University Press (2nd edition, 2018).